

**THE MAIN FACTORS MAKE EFFECTIVE EFL LEARNING
MATERIALS AND THEIR TRANSLATED VERSIONS COMFORTABLE
FOR LANGUAGE LEARNERS**

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Annotation: *The thesis discusses the importance of making learning materials comfortable for language learners. Taking into account students' needs and adapting teaching materials to their level are main factors of establishing effective learning process.*

Key words: *language acquisition, relaxed, anxiety, supportive, inclusiveness, voice.*

Research has shown the results of different forms of anxiety on acquisition: the less anxious the learner, the better language acquisition proceeds. Also, relaxed and comfortable students can learn effectively more in shorter periods of time (Dulay, Burt and Krashen 1982).

Although it is obvious that pressure can motivate and stimulate some types of language learners, but most language learners acquire effectively from feeling at ease and that they lose desire for language learning when they feel anxious, uncomfortable or tense (see, for example, Oxford 1999).

Some materials developers argue that it is the obligatory task of the teacher to help the learners to feel comfort and that the materials themselves can do very little to help. but a teaching process shows quite different evidence that materials can help learners to feel at ease in a number of ways. For instance, most learners feel more comfortable with written materials with lots of white space and colorful pictures, shapes related to a current context than they do with materials in which lots of various activities are crammed together on the same page. Moreover, language learners are more at ease with texts and illustrations that they find any closeness to thir own culture than they are with those which seem to them to be culturally alien; “Students are more relaxed with materials which are obviously trying to help them to learn than they are with materials which are always testing them. Feeling at ease can also be achieved through a ‘voice’ which is relaxed and supportive, through content and activities which encourage the personal participation of the learners, through materials which relate the world of the book to the world of the learner and through the absence of activities which could threaten self-esteem and cause humiliation (Brian Tomlinson, 2011). Some material developers additionally claim that the most essential (and possibly least researched) factor is that of the ‘voice’ of the materials. Conventionally, language-learning materials are de-voiced and anonymous. They are usually written in a semiformal style and show very little about the personality, interests and experiences of the writer. They recommend to materials writers do is to chat to the learners casually in the same way that good teachers do and to try to achieve personal contact with them by revealing their own preferences, interests and opinions. and try to achieve a personal voice (Beck, McKeown and Worthy 1995) by ensuring that what they say to the learners contains such features of morality; informal discourse features (e.g. contracted forms, informal lexis); the active rather than the passive voice; concreteness (e.g. examples, anecdotes); inclusiveness (e.g. not signalling intellectual, linguistic or cultural superiority over the learners).

Nowadays, Uzbek students are offered several English grammar books which translated into Uzbek. According to the factors discussed above these translated versions of English grammar books have several advantages. Firstly, these books are primary handout material for the learners who is putting their very first step to acquire language and desire to learn its grammar. Secondly, beginners who prefer doing self study can find them easy to understand without an instructor. Main disadvantage of these types of books is possible existence of errors and mistakes in explanation and translation. However, EFL teachers may use translated grammar book simultaneously with original ones on the basis of comparison.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Brian Tomlinson, "Materials Development in Language Teaching", Cambridge University Press, 2011
2. Heidi Dulay, Marina Burt and Stephen Krashen, "Language Two", Oxford University Press España, S.A. January 1, 1982
3. Beck, Isabel L., Margaret G. McKeown, and Jo Worthy. "Giving a Text Voice Can Improve Students' Understanding", Reading Research Quarterly, 1995